

A review of the spider species *Cheiracanthium furculatum* (Araneae: Cheiracanthiidae)

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ABSTRACT

Cheiracanthium furculatum is an African species described by Karsch (1879) from Gabon. It occurs widely throughout Africa, and was introduced in several European countries. They are free-running plant-dwellers that play an important role in agroecosystems. In southern Africa they are very commonly found in houses, where they come into contact with humans and deliver bites at night. Unfortunately, misinformation on the species is circulating widely, particularly causing problems concerning their medical importance. Detailed information on their morphology, behaviour, distribution, and medical and environmental importance is provided.

Key words: agroecosystem, grapes, medical importance, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), synanthropic, yellow sac spider

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Cheiracanthium* C.L. Koch, 1839 is widely known, with 214 species globally (World Spider Catalog 2021). From the Afrotropical Region 19 species are recognized. They are known as yellow or long-legged sac spiders, due to the sac-like retreats they build. In this paper, we focus on the species *C. furculatum* Karsch, 1879, which is widespread throughout Africa, Madagascar and the Comoros, and the Cape Verde Islands.

Cheiracanthium furculatum is one of the best sampled and studied spider species in southern Africa. This includes their medical and environmental importance. Unfortunately, misinformation on the species is circulating widely, causing problems about their medical importance and accurate diagnosis of bites (Du Plessis & Reuter 2021). In this paper, we provide detailed information on the morphology, behaviour, distribution, and medical and environmental importance of this particular species.

Data obtained over a period of 50 years were used. The three authors were all involved with museum collections. Primary data sampled with the specimens contains valuable information on their distribution and general behaviour. The authors were also involved in the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Foord *et al.* 2011; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015). Through SANSA, the First Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2011) and First Spider Red List (Foord *et al.* 2020) have been compiled. As part of SANSA, a Virtual Museum was developed to document the photographs submitted by the public. It presently contains >4000 images submitted by >100 photographers (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012).

TAXONOMY

The genus *Cheiracanthium* was first placed in the Clubionidae, but it was transferred to the Miturgidae by Ramírez (1997) and then to the Eutichuridae by Ramírez (2014). Presently, Cheiracanthiidae is recognized as the valid family name.

In a revision of the *Cheiracanthium* of the Afrotropical Region, Lotz (2007) examined 925 specimens from 21 museum collections. In older publications, *Cheiracanthium lawrencei* Roewer, 1951 was the species commonly mentioned from South Africa. However, *C. lawrencei* Roewer, 1951 was a replacement name for *Cheiracanthium*

Figure 1. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* female (Photo: P. Webb).

Figure 2. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* male (Photo: P. Webb).

inornatum Lawrence, 1927, a preoccupied name (O. Pickard-Cambridge 1874). In this revision, Lotz (2007) synonymized ten species with *C. furculatum*, including *C. lawrencei*. This gives an indication on how widespread the species is.

MORPHOLOGY

Cheiracanthium furculatum are two-clawed, medium-sized spiders (females TL 7–12 mm, males 5–11 mm), recognized by their uniform creamish-yellow bodies with chelicerae and eye area blackish-brown (Figs 1, 2); eyes in two rows, fovea indistinct; chelicerae robust with long fangs (Figs 3, 6); abdomen without long curved erect setae anterodorsally and with distinct heart-mark; leg I longer than IV; male palp with long cymbial and retrolateral tibial apophyses (Fig. 4); female genitalia with small, well-separated spermathecae (Fig. 5).

Fig. 3. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* female, anterior view (Photo: P. Webb)

Figures 4-6. *Cheiracanthium furculatum*: 4. Male palp; 5. Epigyne; 6. Chelicerae.

DISTRIBUTION

Cheiracanthium furculatum is the most widely distributed species of the genus in Africa. It has been collected from almost all terrestrial habitats and biomes, except habitats such as deserts and caves (Lotz 2007). So far it has been collected from Angola, Botswana, Cape Verde, Comores, D.R. Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Ethiopia, Gabon, Kenya, Mali, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, South Africa, Swaziland, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia and Zimbabwe (Lotz 2007) (Fig. 7). A specimen was also collected at Marion Island in the southern Atlantic Ocean (Khoza *et al.* 2005).

Figure 7. Distribution of *Cheiracanthium furculatum* in Africa (from Lotz 2007).

The species has recently been recorded in Europe, from Belgium (Bosselaers 2013), Germany (Bayer 2014) and Poland (Rozwałka *et al.* 2017). Specimens of *C. furculatum* were found in grapes imported from South Africa. The scale of this import is probably quite large. Although spiders may be of benefit as predators in vineyards, they may also pose problems as possible invasive species when they land up in containers of table grapes and are inadvertently exported. When the grapes are harvested, some spiders escape detection during the packing process by hiding in silk retreats made in bunches of grapes. The grapes are chilled prior to export, causing the spiders to become dormant and immobile. Spiders are able to lower their metabolic rates, enabling them to survive long periods of exposure to low temperatures. When the exported containers are opened at the retailers or by consumers in recipient countries, the spiders may escape after this period of inactivity (Fig. 8). According to Rozwałka *et al.* (2017), the climatic conditions in Central and Western Europe exclude an acclimatization of *C. furculatum* in the wild, but it is likely that this species may be settling in the south of the continent. However, with climate change prevailing, things might change.

Figure 8. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* from exported grapes.

Distribution in South Africa: Four-hundred of the adult specimens (43%) examined by Lotz (2007: 25-28) came from South Africa. In Table 1 the number of specimens and percentage of total specimens examined from each province are shown. The majority of specimens were from Gauteng (40 %) and the Free State (23 %) (Table 1).

Table 1. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* records from the nine provinces in South Africa, based on data from Lotz (2007).

PROVINCE	SPECIMENS	%
GAUTENG	159	39.8
FREE STATE	91	22.8
NORTHWEST	63	15.8
KWAZULU-NATAL	31	7.8
EASTERN CAPE	20	5.0
LIMPOPO	14	3.5
WESTERN CAPE	11	2.8
MPUMALANGA	6	1.5
NORTHERN CAPE	5	1.3
TOTAL	400	

This data corresponds with the SANSA database (2021) on the distribution of *C. furculatum* in South Africa, as shown in Fig. 9. For more detailed distribution data see Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2021).

Figure 9. Distribution of *Cheiracanthium furculatum* in South Africa (after Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010).

BEHAVIOUR: IMPORTANCE AS AGROBIONT SPECIES

They are nocturnal, free-running hunters, hiding in a silk sac-shaped retreat made on plants (Fig. 10), frequently in rolled-up leaves, when not active (Lotz 2007; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014). Four types of sac retreats are made and used for resting, mating, breeding and hibernating. During the period the eggs develop, the female encloses herself with the eggs to guard them.

Figure 10. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* female on sac retreat (Photo: P. Webb).

Cheiracanthium spp. play an important role in agroecosystems throughout the world. They are aggressive feeders. This was confirmed by Rozwałka *et al.* (2017), who remarked that the species showed aggressive behaviour during breeding experiments. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* is the dominant sac spider recorded from crops in South Africa, and is recognized as an agrobiont species in vineyards and pistachio nuts (Haddad *et al.* 2005; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2013). It is also the dominant sac spider recorded from citrus in South Africa (Van den Berg *et al.* 1992). Their silk retreats, which are usually constructed between rolled up leaves, frequently trap citrus psylla (Van den Berg *et al.* 1992).

The species was also collected during cotton surveys (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 1999). In the laboratory they preyed on all larval stages of the cotton bollworm. During feeding studies they killed more than 200 *Spodoptera* larvae in a short period of time, but not always feeding on them. According to Brettell & Burgess (1973), *C. furculatum* was frequently found in the narrow space between the bract and boll of cotton in Zimbabwe. They were also sampled from avocado, citrus, cotton, lucerne, macadamia, maize, mango, pecans, pistachio, potatoes, strawberries, tomatoes and vineyards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2013).

BEHAVIOUR: IN HOUSES

We found that *C. furculatum* make their retreats in houses during the day in the folds of material such as curtains, bedding and clothes. The spider will also use gaps between books and magazines or even a corner to make their retreats. At the NCA we have frequently received specimens collected from curtain folds in a house, and up to seven specimens per house were sometimes collected.

Queries to the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) and the National Museum in Bloemfontein (NMBA) about spiders in and around houses were frequently accompanied with reports of bites. More than 1000 records of spiders recorded from houses and gardens were extracted from the databases at the two collections, as well as information from the Identification Service and Virtual Museum. Of these species, only species of 10 genera can be considered as permanent house-dwellers. However, most of them are too small to harm people or their behaviour does not bring them directly into contact with humans. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* is by far the most abundant species (>500 specimens, 52%) sampled from houses in the Gauteng and the Free State provinces, while they occur in low numbers from the three Cape provinces (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz 2017). Therefore, species' distribution patterns need to be taken into account before any decision about their medical importance can be taken.

MEDICAL IMPORTANCE

Data showed that *C. furculatum* are frequently encountered in houses in parts of South Africa. As they are nocturnal wandering spiders, they come in contact with humans, especially at night when they accidentally land in beds. The first report on *Cheiracanthium* envenomation in southern Africa was provided by De Meillon & Gear (1947). After receiving unexplained report of bites in Gauteng, Dr G. Newlands (then working at the Medical Research Institute and later at the Ditsong Museum) started to investigate spider bites in the Gauteng area. The spider was identified as *C. furculatum* (then *C. lawrencei*). His research resulted in a series of papers (Newlands 1975, 1976, 1977, 1978, 1986; Newlands & Atkinson 1988, 1990a, b; Newlands *et al.* 1980; Snyman & Larsen 2005; Müller *et al.* 2012; Bird *et al.* 2021).

Research on *Cheiracanthium* spp. also formed part of three MSc studies (Lotz 1995; Croucamp 1999; Du Plessis 2019) and a PhD study (Newlands 1986). They found that *C. furculatum* has been implicated in more than 75 % of all spider envenomations in Gauteng (Newlands *et al.* 1980; Lotz 1995). The venom of *C. furculatum* was subjected to a preliminary analysis as part of the Croucamp MSc (Croucamp 1999; Croucamp & Veale 1999). They found the molecular mass of the polypeptides in the range of 14 kDa to 200 kDa, which is not in contradiction with the results of the detailed analysis of *Cheiracanthium punctorium* (Villers, 1789) venom by Vassilevski *et al.* (2010).

The first author started working at the NCA in 1967 and through queries to the ARC-Spider Identification Service the problem of sac spiders in houses was confirmed. The >800 photographs sent in to the Virtual Museum confirms their presence in houses. Reports were also received from people that had been bitten. The bites occurred at night while the individuals were sleeping and when they move around in bed, disturbing the spider. The patient is often not immediately aware of being bitten, as the bite is not very painful, but fang marks and bleeding usually confirm the bite.

The first author was bitten on three occasions. From reports from the public, the bites are usually not painful and usually happened at night; the victim was often not aware of being bitten. The bite site first resembles a mosquito or flea bite, and sometimes two fang bite-marks are visible (Fig. 11). A typical bull's-eye lesion develops and the surrounding area gradually becomes swollen, red and painful (Fig. 12). The centre of wound undergoes necrotic changes, leaving an ulcerated wound; local tissue damage and necrosis may be minimal or extensive (severity variable). Systemic symptoms may be experienced after a day or two, e.g. tender lymph nodes, rash, low-grade fever, headache, muscle and joint pain. After a couple of days the lesion may resemble a furuncle or carbuncle. In most cases the process is self-limiting. In the minority of cases the local lesion may be complicated by an aggressive, spreading cellulitis and a subcutaneous suppuration. The necrotic tissue detaches after about 2-3 weeks. On two occasions bites were reported where the spider was caught but no necrosis developed. Like snake bites, these could have been "dry" bites, where no venom is released.

In discussions with several general practitioners and a doctor at an Emergency Unit at a hospital in Pretoria, this type of wound (Figs 10, 11) is very commonly encountered. In Fig. 11, the two bite entry points made by the fangs are clear. Unfortunately, there is no institution in Gauteng and the Free State to document accurate records of bites, as is found at the Tygerberg Poison Information Centre in Cape Town. The Tygerberg Poison Information Centre reported only three sac spider bites over a period of four years (Müller *et al.* 2017). However, the lack of bite reports can be explained by *C. furculatum* being quite rare and sparsely distributed in the Western Cape (Fig. 7; Table 1).

Figure 11. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* bite, showing the two fang marks.

Figure 12. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* bite, showing the swollen, red area around the bite site after two days.

CONCLUSION

The majority of suspected *C. furculatum* bites among humans are unintentional and mostly harmless. The bites are not life threatening and are usually self-healing. It must be kept in mind that these could be more serious illnesses (Du Plessis & Heal 2021).

Dermonecrotic arachnidism is the potential cutaneous reaction to spider bite venom. The yellow sac spider, genus *Cheiracanthium*, is historically considered capable of inducing dermonecrotic lesions. However, this has been debated. In Vetter *et al.* (2006), for example, the research results from *C. furculatum* were questioned, because they did not fit in with the two *Cheiracanthium* species studied in the U.S.A. Since then, several case studies have been published on *Cheiracanthium* bites in Europe (Divito *et al.* 2009; Papini 2012; Nentwig *et al.* 2013; Varl *et al.* 2017).

In South Africa, the Vetter article was unfortunately followed by some, leading to the spread of misinformation regarding *C. furculatum*. An example is the statement "the early 1980's **supposed bites** from the common House Sac spider *Cheiracanthium furculatum* have been believed to be medically important and to cause slow-healing (necrotic) sores. This reputation came about from a **study** conducted several decades ago using **circumstantial evidence**. How the researchers proved that the sores were caused by a spider bite is not recorded. The **media** got hold of this research, it was repeated many times in both scientific and popular literature without rigorous investigation, and a legend was born" (Leroy 2015).

However this information is wrong as we now know the following about *C. furculatum*:

- It is a species with a wide distribution throughout Africa and the surrounding islands.
- It was recently introduced to several European countries through export grapes from South Africa and Morocco.
- It is an important predator sampled from agroecosystems.
- It is a species that is commonly found in houses in parts of South Africa.
- It is a species with a disjunct distribution pattern in South Africa, with most specimens recorded from the Gauteng and Free State Provinces.
- It is the most abundant species (>501 specimens, 52%) sampled from houses in the Gauteng and the Free State Provinces.
- In houses they make silk retreats in folds of material during the day and are easily seen and collected.
- They are aggressive medium-sized spiders with strong fangs.
- At night they wander around, frequently landing in bedding.
- In the Gauteng and the Free State Provinces bites are frequently reported.
- Although not life threatening, the bite can cause a lot of discomfort, pain and necrosis.
- It is a species that we recommend be removed from houses.

Also, the decision that a spider bite is only registered as a bite when the spider is collected is not correct, as it will exclude bites received at night by nocturnal species. The specific aggression of the spider species and the adaptation of the species to human environments must also be taken into account, and then *Cheiracanthium furculatum* meets all these criteria.

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